

THE DOCTRINE OF SUFISM IN THE EYES OF THE SCHOLARS OF THE EAST

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the interpretation of the doctrine of Sufism by Eastern scholars, their philosophical, ethical and spiritual views on this issue. In particular, the works of such scholars as Ahmad Yassavi, Najmiddin Kubro, Bahouddin Naqshband on Sufism, their ideological principles in this direction and their contribution to the concept of a perfect person are considered. The article reveals the place and significance of this doctrine in Eastern thought, based on the thoughts of scholars who have illuminated Sufism not only as a religious, but also as a socio-spiritual system. The role of Sufism in spiritual purification, moral maturity and establishing peace in society is also analyzed.*

Keywords: *Sufism, religion, Ahmad Yassavi, Najmiddin Kubro, Bahouddin Naqshband, Abu Mansur al-Moturidi, Burhoniddin al-Marginani.*

Introduction. In ancient Turan, the scientific, spiritual and spiritual power was so strong that it could not be destroyed by various invasions, aggressions and evils. Even in such conditions, our ancestors preserved the historically formed rich cultural-spiritual and scientific heritage, national values and traditions and enriched it further. If we look at the pages of our past history, the works of our great ancestors, who studied the civilization of not only our people, but also the countries of the whole world and wrote down their relations with their history and culture with respect and reverence have reached us.

Sufism occupies a special place in the thinking of Eastern thinkers. For centuries, this doctrine has promoted the spiritual perfection, moral purification and spiritual growth of a person as the main criterion. In particular, scholars such as Ahmad Yassavi, Najmiddin Kubro, Bahouddin Naqshband, Abu Mansur al-Moturidi, Burhoniddin al-Marginani deeply analyzed the place and role of Sufism in the formation of human personality in their works. According to

them, Sufism is not just a religious path, but a complex spiritual and practical system aimed at educating a perfect person.

Sufism is associated with the name of Yusuf Hamadani (1048-1140), an Islamic scholar who lived and worked in the 11th-12th centuries, and later created sects such as Yassaviya, Naqshbandiya and Kubraviya. Yusuf Hamadani lived in Bukhara for a long time and mentored Ahmad Yassavi, Abdukholiq Gijduvani and other great scholars. Later, he developed some rules of Khojagan-Naqshbandiya order.

The sect of Ahmad Yassavi (1005-1166) occupies a great place in the history of the culture of Turkish people. Ahmad Yassavi described his sect in a poetic style in his work entitled "Devoni hikmat". Yassavi's teachings put forward the idea that one can reach God's presence by living a life with purity, honesty, correctness, kindness, strength of one's own hand and skin on one's forehead. The teaching of Yassaviya condemns some people's greed for wealth, calls for humility and generosity. Thus, Ahmad Yassavi found the first mysticism in Central Asia and contributed to the development of Islam.

Mysticism, Yassavi's philosophical worldview in the great thinker's work "Devoni Hikmat", which has a very deep and rich content, captivates the reader's attention with all its being. He himself did not write any book under the name "Devoni Hikmat". This rare work was collected and organized by his disciples and followers.

In "Devoni Hikmat" the concepts of divine love and infatuation, enlightenment and reaching from the mortal world to the eternal world are delivered in sincere and touching tones. In his opinion, "Knowing oneself, not the words of the truth" is the main task. That is why the sage says that a Sufi who seeks the pleasure of this world is not a Sufi, only a person who obeys and prays, preaches honesty and purity and lives with the concern of the people is a real Sufi.

Another compatriot who made a significant contribution to the development of Islam is Najmiddin Kubro (1145-1221), who was born in Khiva, Khorezm. In the science of Islamic studies, his teaching is known as the Kubraviya sect. Najmiddin Kubro, who was knowledgeable from his youth, studied in Egypt, Iran and other countries of the East. His contribution to Islam is that he introduced the method of performing zikr without making a sound (khufiya). The Kubraviya sect is based on hadith and sharia. According to this doctrine, man forms a small world with his essence and embodies everything in the universe, which is a big world.

Sufism formed on the basis of Islam, especially Naqshbandi served as the ideological basis of the spirituality of that time. Based on Islam, Naqshbandiya promoted the ideas that open a wide way for a person to acquire moral purity, work and knowledge and had a great positive

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significance in spiritual and social life. Naqshbandi theorists such as Bahavuddin Naqshband, Khoja Muhammad Porso, Khoja Akrom lived and worked during this period.

The sect that arose in the field of Sufism in Central Asia in the XIV century is associated with the name of Khoja Muhammad Bahovuddin Naqshband (1318-1389). Bahovuddin Naqshband was born in 1318 in the village of Qasri Hinduvan near Bukhara (later it was called Qasri Orifon in honor of Naqshband). Voluntary poverty is the foundation of the Naqshband doctrine. According to Y. E. Bertels, a famous oriental scholar, he lived by farming all his life and planted wheat on his small plot of land in his village and did not keep any property or wealth in his house. The original creed of Naqshbandi doctrine is “Dil ba yoru, dast ba kor”, which means “Always keep your heart in Allah and your hands in work”. In the 15th century, the Naqshbandi doctrine spread widely in Muslim countries such as Afghanistan, Iran, and India. Supporters of this doctrine were against asceticism and the tyranny of the rich and nobles. At the same time, they encouraged people to engage in all useful and auspicious activities such as trade, agriculture, handicrafts, literature, music, science, calligraphy, painting, miniature painting, and construction.

Another great ancestor of ours who made a great contribution to the development of Islam is Abu Mansur Muhammad ibn Muhammad al-Hanafi al-Maturidi (870-944), the founder of the largest Sunni school of theology in the Muslim world. In 2000, the 1130th anniversary of Moturidi's birth was widely celebrated. Moturidi's contribution to the development of Islam is that the Hanafi stream was formed by the followers of the al-Moturidi school.

The most famous scientists of the world unanimously recognized al-Moturidi as one of the great representatives of the science of the word. One of Al-Moturidi's masterpieces, “Kitab al-Tawhid” (or “The Book of Monotheism”) is considered to be the first work in Muslim theology to explain the theory of knowledge. Most of the works of Abu Mansur al-Moturidi have not reached us or those that have reached us are mainly kept in libraries and manuscript collections of foreign countries. The book “Kitab al-Tawhid”, which is considered very important in the Islamic world, has reached us in its entirety.

Burkhaniddin al-Marginani (1123-1197) is another scholar who made a significant contribution to the development of Islam in Central Asia. Our compatriot al-Marginani, who created the scientific foundations of fiqh (law) in the Islamic world, was born on September 23, in 1123. He is known by the names of Burhan ud-din wa-l-milla and Burhoniddin al-Marginani because he perfectly mastered the sciences of the Kur'an and hadith and created fundamental works.

Al-Marginani's contribution to the development of Islam is particularly significant in Islamic jurisprudence. This is related to his work "Hidaya" written in Samarkand in 1178. In "Hidaya" the solution of legal issues is first given by the statement of the opinions of famous jurists and the objections or additions of other authors to it. Based on the opinions of these reputable authors, the way to choose the best solution for a specific issue was followed. In this way, not only the exact expression of the law, but also the perfect interpretation is based on it.

Conclusion

In conclusion, I would like to say that, Mysticism is a teaching that contains the deep philosophical aspect of Islamic spiritual life, which is important in the way of getting closer to Allah, purifying the soul and becoming a perfect human being. Scholars of the East paid close attention to this direction and analyzed it not only religiously, but also morally and philosophically.

Through the teachings of Sufism, the scholars of the East called people to perfection and society to moral maturity. Even today, this teaching has not lost its relevance as a source of promoting spiritual perfection, peace and tolerance.

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